

Satisfaction of Stall Owners in the Operations of the Public Market

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Abstract:

The study aimed to determine level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market of the first-class City in Negros Occidental for Calendar Year 2024 as basis for a development plan. Using a descriptive research design, 150 public market vendors selected through purposive sampling responded to a validated and reliable survey. Data analysis utilized SPSS, with tools like frequency counts, percentages, means, and the Mann-Whitney U test. Results revealed that most respondents were older females with lower educational attainment and shorter tenancy. Stall owners expressed high satisfaction with public market operations, particularly in peace and order, market layout, and health and sanitation. However, areas needing improvement include the provision of additional resources, such as Barangay Tanods for enhanced security, emergency equipment like fire extinguishers, and better facilities for hygiene, such as more handwashing stations. The study found no significant differences in satisfaction levels based on age, sex, educational attainment, or tenancy length. Recommendations include deploying more Barangay Tanods to ensure safety, installing emergency equipment to address market layout concerns, and improving health and sanitation through accessible handwashing stations and consistent maintenance of cleanliness. Monthly monitoring and evaluations are advised to ensure adherence to standards and continuous improvement. These recommendations aim to enhance market conditions, promote safety, and improve overall satisfaction and well-being for both stall owners and consumers.

Keywords: Stall Owner Satisfaction, Public Market Operations, Vendor Experience

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The World Economic Forum (2021) highlighted that global capital markets are undergoing transformation due to various interrelated forces, especially following the pandemic and uneven economic recovery. These changes include the democratization of public markets, increased access to private market opportunities, and growing concerns about data security, financial intermediation, and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) transparency. Meanwhile, the Philippines-Country Commercial Guide (2022) noted that the country's market remains challenging due to underdeveloped infrastructure and a lagging regulatory system compared to its regional neighbors.

At the local level, initiatives like Iloilo City's efforts to modernize public markets through public-private partnerships show a drive toward improved facilities that address long-standing issues such as traffic, flooding, and sanitation (Manila Times, 2022). However, these improvements are not uniformly felt. In contrast, vendors in Mandaue public market expressed frustration over inconsistent government policies, such as frequent changes in entry and exit schedules and pandemic-related restrictions, which they claim have negatively impacted their income and operations (Sagarino, 2021).

In Bago City, as the main residence of the researcher, the Public Market was restored by the City Government after an incident where half of the stalls were burned in the back area of the building during the pandemic. An infrastructure of buildings was put up to accommodate vendors and reduce congestion. The occupancy of vendors in the public market has been for almost two (2) years after restoration.

As beneficiary of the facility provided by the city government of Bago and services rendered by the vendors, the issues and gaps presented above encourages me to conduct a study in order to have basis on the satisfaction level of vendors regarding public market operational system so that a development plan can be made based on the findings of the study. Likewise, one of the recipients of the public market, the output that can be made, may benefit the consumers, vendors, and the whole city in general.

Current State of Knowledge

The satisfaction of stall owners in public market operations is influenced by several factors, notably peace and order, market management, and physical layout. Studies show that inclusive governance involving vendors in decision-making fosters trust and collaboration with authorities, enhancing market order and vendor satisfaction (Forkuor, Akuoko, & Yeboah, 2017; Kurniadi & Ibrahim, 2023). Formalizing vendor activities by integrating them into official economic structures and providing designated spaces reduces conflicts and improves working conditions (Falla & Valencia, 2019). Well-planned market layouts that improve accessibility and reduce congestion significantly contribute to higher satisfaction among stall owners (Sandhika, Sholihah, & Yuli, 2024; Peimani & Kamalipour, 2022; Anafo et al., 2024; Suryanto et al., 2022). Hygiene practices, supported by training, also enhance vendor satisfaction by fostering consumer trust and reducing health risks (Okojie & Isah, 2019; Ziblim & Yakubu, 2022). Vendors play a critical role in urban economies by providing employment, reducing poverty, and supplying goods, particularly for those excluded from formal sectors due to limited education or skills (Grant, 2023; Babu & Kiran, 2019; Jaishankar & Sujatha, 2016; Njaya, 2014). Their contributions to economic development and social mobility highlight the importance of addressing operational challenges to improve their satisfaction and livelihood.

Moreover, maintaining peace and order in public markets is crucial for stall owners' satisfaction, as conflicts between vendors and authorities can hinder effective governance and reduce satisfaction (Agnes, 2023). Studies highlight that enforcing cleanliness, sanitation, and security standards significantly boosts both vendor and customer satisfaction (Dela Cruz, 2021). Additionally, well-planned stall layouts that enhance accessibility and reduce overcrowding improve vendor productivity and customer flow, leading to greater satisfaction (Reyes, 2020; Desucatan et al., 2023). However, weak local governance and insufficient legal protections often exacerbate vendors' challenges, negatively affecting their satisfaction and sense of security (Solidum, 2023).

Further, studies emphasize that well-organized market layouts and clear management policies significantly improve vendor satisfaction by reducing conflicts and enhancing interactions with authorities (Sandhika, 2024; Putro et al., 2023). Effective stall arrangements and accessibility boost operational efficiency and overall market functionality. However, research from various countries highlights persistent gaps in food safety knowledge and sanitation practices among vendors, posing health risks and diminishing vendor satisfaction (Ma et al., 2019; Nkosi & Tabit, 2021; Vero, 2024). These findings underscore the importance of comprehensive training programs and regular monitoring to improve hygiene standards, public health, and the market environment.

Lastly, research across various Philippine cities highlights that while market vendors generally have positive attitudes and reasonable practices toward food safety and hygiene, gaps in ongoing education and sanitation implementation persist, affecting vendor satisfaction and public health (Gonzales, 2020; Jose & Villanueva, 2023; Adrales et al., 2022). Studies also show that physical stall design and layout significantly influence both vendor satisfaction and customer accessibility (Agustin, 2016; Malilay et al., 2024). Additionally, challenges in law enforcement and local security, including inefficiencies among Barangay Tanods and Police Security Officers, undermine peace and order in markets, contributing to stall owners' dissatisfaction and reduced trust in authorities (Recio & Gomez, 2013; Sumad-On, 2024; Austria-Cruz, 2020). Overall, improving hygiene practices, market layouts, and security support is crucial to enhancing vendor satisfaction.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study is anchored in the role of expectancy-disconfirmation in satisfaction by Anderson (1980) cited by Van de Walle (2017) which states that satisfaction can only be interpreted in conjunction with knowledge about prior expectations that are predictions of future performance, or an anticipation of what will follow, that exist prior to the service experienced. The expectancy-disconfirmation model has become the predominant approach in explaining citizen satisfaction with public services. This theory posits a brief idea about citizen satisfaction with public services and provides valuable information about the relationship among expectations, perceived service quality/performance, disconfirmation, and satisfaction. This theory served as the basis for determining the level of satisfaction of stall owners.

Objectives

The study aimed to determine level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market of the first-class City in Negros Occidental for Calendar Year 2024 as basis for a development plan. More specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the respondents' profile in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants; 2) the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market according to the area of maintenance of peace and order, market layout stalls, and health and sanitation; 3) the significant difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market when grouped and compared according to the following variables.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study aimed to determine level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of public market of the first-class City in Negros Occidental for Calendar Year 2024. Due to the nature of the problem of the study, a descriptive research design was used. According to Dudovskiy (2017), descriptive research design attempts to determine, describe, or identify characteristics within the field of investigation. Descriptive research sought to determine differences between or among study variables, explore causes of phenomena, test hypotheses, and develop generalizations, principles, or theories based on findings. The nature of this study determined the condition of things in their present state. Based on the above premise, the researcher considered using the descriptive research design most appropriate.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were 150 vendors in the public market. Purposive sampling was utilized. A purposive sample is a non-probability sample selected based on a population's characteristics and the study's objectives. This sampling strategy can be beneficial when a specific sample must be attained promptly, and proportions are not essential (Crossman, 2020).

Instruments

The researcher utilized a self-made survey questionnaire to collect data on respondents' profiles and stall owners' satisfaction with public market operations. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part I gathered demographic information such as age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of tenancy, while Part II assessed satisfaction levels across three areas—maintenance of peace and order, market stall layout, and health and sanitation—each with ten items. Stall owners rated their satisfaction using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("almost never") to 5 ("always"). The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.74-excellent) and reliability (0.833-good). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

After confirming the instrument's validity and reliability, the researcher made enough copies to distribute to the study's respondents. The quantitative data in this study were gathered using a survey questionnaire. According to Good, as referenced by Vega (2015), a questionnaire is a systematic set of written questions on a given subject, with a place given for each answer.

A letter of permission was sent to the city mayor, requesting permission to undertake a research study to determine the level of satisfaction of stall owners with the operation of public markets. The letter of authorization will be included in the market vendors' letter. Upon approval, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to target respondents in a face-to-face mode of investigation and instructed the participants to fill out all of the items throughout the questionnaire delivery.

Additionally, the raw data were converted into a numerical format under the guidance of a coding manual to assess the level of consumer satisfaction. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software and Microsoft Excel were used to compute encoded data. Also, statistics tables were created considering the issues raised in this inquiry.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective 1 employed descriptive analytical scheme and frequency and percentage distributions to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables: age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay of tenants.

Objective 2 utilized descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of satisfaction of stall owners in public market operations in terms of the following areas: maintenance of peace and order, market layout, stalls, and health and sanitation.

Objective 3 used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine whether or not significant differences exist in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in public market operations when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Participants in the study agreed to participate and were given time to reflect on it and ask any questions they had. As a result, the respondents were fully informed on the study's overall purpose. The participants were not in any way harmed or compromised, whether physically or psychologically. Furthermore, respondents were informed that the collected data would be kept confidential or anonymous. Finally, the gathered data is thoroughly processed without collecting personally identifiable details. The researcher provided critical information about the study's beginning and the details about the subject of study. Respondents can freely withdraw from the research study at any time.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Profile of the Respondents According to the Variables Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, and Length of Stay as Tenants

Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (less than 46 years)	69	46.00
	Older (46 years and above)	81	54.00
	Total	150	100
Sex	Male	73	48.70
	Female	77	51.30
	Total	150	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Primary and Secondary Level)	96	64.00
	Higher (College Level)	54	36.00
	Total	150	100
Length of Stay as Tenants	Shorter (below 10 years)	77	51.30
	Longer (10 years and above)	73	48.70
	Total	150	100

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents, as for age, 69 or 46% of the respondents are in the younger category, while 81 or 54% are in the older category. For the variable sex, 73 or 48.70% belong to the male category, while 77 or 51.30% belong to the female category. Furthermore, for the highest educational attainment, 96 or 64% are in the lower educational attainment, while 54 or 36% belong to a higher educational attainment. Moreover, 73 or 48.70% belong to the shorter category for the length of stay as tenants, while 77 or 51.30 % fall under the longer category. The study reveals that most respondents were older females with lower educational attainment and shorter stays as tenants in the public market as stall owners.

Level of Satisfaction of Stall Owners in the Operation of the Public Market in the Area of Maintenance of Peace and Order, Market Layout Stalls, and Health and Sanitation

Table 2

Level of Satisfaction of Stall Owners in the Operation of the Public Market as to Maintenance of Peace and Order

Items	Means	Interpretation
<i>As a public market vendor, I find that areas for selling is...</i>		
1. properly managed by guidelines and rules for occupancy.	4.02	High Level
2. guided with security measure with the presence of PNP personnel in the area.	3.73	High Level
3. provided with the presence of force multiplier or Brgy. Tanod in lieu of police officer.	2.97	Moderate Level
4. fully equipped with signages as to implementation of the policy/ordinance/law.	3.82	High Level

5. conducive and convenient both for vendors and consumers.	4.14	High Level
6. equally provided to vendors of the same level/category.	4.00	High Level
7. humanely implemented according to the needs and security of the vendors.	3.98	High Level
8. provided with the parking area to avoid untoward traffic congestion and accident.	3.87	High Level
9. safe and secured for snatchers and pick pocketers.	3.77	High Level
10. provided a permanent police outpost for any untoward incidence in the whole vicinity with personnel rendering 24/7 services.	3.79	High Level
TOTAL	3.81	High Level

As shown in Table 2, the overall mean score was 3.81, interpreted as a high level. The respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.14 on Item No. 5 which states, "conductive and convenient both for vendors and consumers, interpreted as high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 2.97 was on Item No. 3, which states "provided with the presence of force multiplier or Brgy. Tanod instead of police officer" is interpreted as a moderate level.

The result implies that stall owners in the operation of the public market in the maintenance of peace and order are revealed at a high level, specifically in terms of conduciveness and convenience for both the vendors and consumers; however, a need for the provision of a force multiplier, a Brgy. Tanod, instead of a police officer, absence should be considered.

Sumad-On (2024) researched the Central Region of Angadanan, Isabela, finding that Barangay Tanods were only moderately efficient in crime prevention. Incorrect regular duties, a lack of suitable orientation, and limited equipment caused this poor performance. Stall owners may lose trust in Tanods' capacity to maintain peace and order, thus impacting overall satisfaction.

Similarly, Austria-Cruz (2020) investigated the efficiency of Barangay Police Security Officers (BPSOs) and found a need for improved training programs and higher pay. The research emphasized that Tanods may fail to fulfill their tasks successfully without sufficient training and support, possibly leading to dissatisfaction among community members, particularly stall owners.

Table 3

Level of Satisfaction of Stall Owners in the Operation of the Public Market as to Market Layout Stalls

Items	Means	Interpretation
<i>As a public market vendor, I find that the market layout stalls is...</i>		
1. convenient and safe for display of goods/items.	3.97	High Level
2. spacious for serving both the vendors and the costumers.	3.95	High Level
3. properly supported with equipment in cases of emergency like fire extinguisher and the like.	3.14	Moderate Level
4. with adequate number of washrooms both for operators and customers.	3.69	High Level
5. availing facilities with specific dimension for the stall space for equity among vendors.	3.92	High Level
6. provided with the availability of office area in the public market for accommodation of vendors' concern.	3.76	High Level
7. provided with the availability of the signages for operators and customers information and dissemination drive.	3.94	High Level
8. provided with clear exits and passageways in case of emergencies.	3.98	High Level
9. fully installed with lightings in and out of vicinity areas.	4.10	High Level
10. well-ventilated that provide conducive environment for the vendors as well as the consumers/market goers.	4.09	High Level
Over-all Mean	3.85	High Level

As reflected in Table 3, the overall mean score on the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market as to market layout stalls area was 3.85, interpreted as a high level. The respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.10 on item No. 9, which states "fully installed with lighting in and out of vicinity areas", interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.14 is on Item No. 3, which states "properly supported with equipment in cases of emergency, like fire extinguisher and the like," interpreted as a moderate level.

This implies that the area of market layouts stalls the provision and installation of equipment in cases of emergency, considering the safety of market owners' stocks and other business resources.

According to Chowdhury et al. (2019), the current fire extinguishing systems in the RDA Market have discovered a lack of complete fire safety measures. The study found that the market lacks critical fire extinguishing devices such as automatic fire extinguishers, sprinkler systems, water reservoirs, fire hydrants, and emergency exits. Only 42 manual fire extinguishers were available, which was insufficient given the size of the market and the flammable items sold. This deficiency created an impression among vendors and customers that the market was unsafe, which might affect stall owners' satisfaction and trust in the market's operations.

Fire incidents in traditional markets have been observed, and many factors that contribute to fire risk have been identified, including a lack of fire extinguishers and local water supplies. The study noted that insufficient fire prevention measures and emergency readiness might result in major property damage and loss of income for stall owners. Such weaknesses endanger vendors' physical safety, affecting their satisfaction and trust in market operations (Rahardjo & Prihantono, 2020).

Table 4

Level of Satisfaction of Stall Owners in the Operation of the Public Market as to Health and Sanitation

Items	Means	Interpretation
<i>As a public market vendor, I find that the health and sanitation is...</i>		
1. provided with accessible hand sink area with running water.	3.47	Moderate Level
2. keeping the walls, floors, ceiling and equipment clean and in good condition at all time.	3.57	High Level
3. having adequate number of garbage containers with plastic liners for operator and customers use.	4.06	High Level
4. regularly maintained the comfort rooms and whole vicinity.	3.69	High Level
5. regularly inspected as to compliance with the health and sanitation protocol.	3.95	High Level
6. equipped with drainage and regular cleaning is practice to ensure sanitation in the area.	3.99	High Level
7. having rules regarding transportation of food and food products among the suppliers within a specific time period.	3.96	High Level
8. having provision of trash containers and regular collections of garbage.	4.03	High Level
9. having rules for the maintenance of cleanliness and sanitation of stalls.	4.05	High Level
10. provided with clean lavatories for both vendors and customers' use.	3.81	High Level
Over-all Mean	3.86	High Level

Table 4 presents the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market in the area of health and sanitation, with an overall mean score of 3.86, which was interpreted as a high level. As revealed in the table, the respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.06 on Item No. 3 which states "having adequate number of garbage containers with plastic liners for operator and customers use" interpreted as high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.47 on Item No. 1, which states "provided with accessible hand sink area with running water," was interpreted as a moderate level.

The results implies that the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market as to health and sanitation area on the provision and accessibility of hand sink area with running water will be given urgent attention for safety, security and compliance on health and sanitation requirement and for the welfare of the community in general.

Okojie and Isah (2019) conducted research in Benin City, Nigeria, to evaluate market sellers' food hygiene knowledge and practices. They discovered that only 71.2% of vending locations had wash basins, and 76.9% had soap provided. The lack of proper handwashing facilities compromises hygiene standards, raising the risk of foodborne infections and undermining customer confidence. This lack of amenities might result in lower customer patronage, directly influencing stall owner satisfaction and income.

Similarly, Nizame et al. (2019) investigated the hygienic standards of market sellers in Bangladesh. Their research found that just 11% of street food vending stalls provided soap and water for handwashing. Furthermore, during food-handling events, no stall sellers cleansed their hands with soap, exposing a serious gap in hygiene precautions. Improper conditions can harm both health and trust between customers, leading to lower profits and vendor satisfaction.

Table 5

The difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the area of maintenance of peace and order when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	69	81.33	2392	0.129		Not Significant
	Older	81	70.53				
Sex	Male	73	75.97	2776.5	0.898		Not Significant
	Female	77	75.06				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	75.08	2552	0.875	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	54	76.24				
Length of Stay as Tenants	Shorter	77	71.1	2472	0.202		Not Significant
	Longer	73	80.14				

The data in Table 5 presents the difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the area of maintenance of peace and order when grouped and compared according to age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants using Mann-Whitney U test.

In terms of age obtained a p-value of 0.129, sex has a p-value of 0.898, highest educational attainment has a p-value of 0.875, and the length of stay as tenants has a p-value of 0.202. is greater than the 0.05 significance level. The result indicated that no significant difference exists. The null hypothesis is, therefore, accepted.

This implies that age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants do not affect the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market in the area maintenance of peace and order.

Solidum (2023) did research on street vendors and discovered no significant differences in responses to governance and legal concerns, workplace-related issues, and physical problems when grouped by household size, daily income, and years of public selling. This shows that these demographic characteristics had no influence on the vendors' evaluations of their work environment and associated obstacles.

Similarly, Kundu et al. (2021) studied the effect of vendors' socio-demographic characteristics on sanitation standards in market businesses. While the study discovered that higher education levels were connected with better hygiene habits, other variables such as sex and age had no significant influence on the hygiene behaviors.

Table 6

The difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the market layout stalls when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	69	78.75	2570	0.397		Not Significant
	Older	81	72.73				
Sex	Male	73	69.60	2485.5	0.221		Not Significant
	Female	77	81.10				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	75.79	2564	0.913	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	54	74.98				
Length of Stay	Shorter	77	72.50	2579.50	0.384		Not Significant

as Tenants	Longer	73	78.66
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Table 6 presents the difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the area of market stall layouts when grouped and compared according to age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants using Mann-Whitney U test.

In terms of age obtained a p-value of 0.397, sex has a p-value of 0.221, highest educational attainment has a p-value of 0.913, and the length of stay as tenants has a p-value of 0.384. is greater than the 0.05 significance level. The result indicated that no significant difference exists. The null hypothesis is, therefore, accepted.

This implies that age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants do not affect the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market in the area market stall layouts.

Piencenaves et al. (2023) studied consumer satisfaction with food vendor sellers in Davao City. The study found that consumers were very satisfied with a variety of factors, including food quality, service quality, pricing and value, environment, and convenience. The survey showed no significant differences in satisfaction levels among customers based on their sociodemographic characteristics, including age, sex, and education level.

Table 7

The difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the health and sanitation when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Intepretation
Age	Younger	69	78.67	2575.5	0.408		Not Significant
	Older	81	72.80				
Sex	Male	73	75.97	2379.5	0.105		Not Significant
	Female	77	75.09				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	96	73.99	2447.5	0.571	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	54	78.18				
Length of Stay as Tenants	Shorter	77	71.53	2505	0.25		Not Significant
	Longer	73	79.68				

Table 7 presents the difference in the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operation of the public market in the area of health and sanitation when grouped and compared according to age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants using Mann-Whitney U test.

In terms of age obtained a p-value of 0.408, sex has a p-value of 0.105, highest educational attainment has a p-value of 0.571, and the length of stay as tenants has a p-value of 0.25. is greater than the 0.05 significance level. The result indicated that no significant difference exists. The null hypothesis is, therefore, accepted.

This implies that age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of stay as tenants do not affect the level of satisfaction of stall owners in the operations of the public market in the area health and sanitation.

Berhe et al. (2020) did a study in the Tigray region of Northern Ethiopia and discovered that just 42.2% of rural residents had a strong understanding of water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) practices. The study found that those with lower educational levels had inadequate information and negative attitudes about cleanliness, which led to poor hand hygiene habits. However, the study found no significant variations in ratings of satisfaction between the sexes.

Conclusions

The study found that most stall owners in the public market were older females with lower educational attainment and shorter tenancy, yet reported high levels of satisfaction with market operations, particularly in peace and order, market layout, and sanitation. No significant difference in satisfaction levels was observed across demographic variables, suggesting that age, sex, education, and length of stay do not affect how stall owners perceive market operations. Despite overall satisfaction, specific concerns were raised, including the need for additional Barangay Tanods to maintain peace and order, installation of emergency equipment like fire extinguishers, and improvements in hygiene facilities such as handwashing stations and overall cleanliness. The study recommends addressing these operational issues and implementing regular monitoring and evaluations to sustain safety, efficiency, and well-being in public market environments.

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